

European Public Local Authorities' Network for
driving the Energy Transition

D7.2 - Visual Identity Handbook

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Executive Summary

ePLANET project is a Coordination and Support Action cofounded by the European Commission through Horizon 2020 program. ePLANET aims to deploy a new clustering governance for energy transition based on a digital framework to share harmonized information, facilitating the adoption of coordinated energy transition actions by the European public sector.

This document defines the visual identity of the project, regarding all its communication and dissemination activities. This includes: logos, types of colours and fonts, template for deliverables and template for presentations. Further releases could be elaborated during project progress if it is considered necessary.

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1 Introduction

The Visual Identity Handbook is part of the activities of Work Package 7, which centralizes most of the coordination and implementation of project's communication and dissemination activities. Work Package 7 consists of different tasks:

- T7.1: Communication and Dissemination plan and coordination
- T7.2: Visual identity
- T7.3: Project website
- T7.4: Promotional material
- T7.5: Conferences
- T7.6: Social media
- T7.7: Newsletters and press releases
- T7.8: Final event

The Visual Identity Handbook will constitute the main reference regarding the graphical layout of the different communication and dissemination materials (e.g. website, deliverables, press releases, presentations). The document includes several key parts:

- Logo, in different versions to maximise compatibility with other communication frameworks.
- Colours and typographies to be prioritised.
- Template for deliverables.
- Template for slideshows and presentations.

2 Logo

The logo plays an important role in the project, because it will represent the identify of ePLANET in all the different communication materials. It is part of all the deliverables and makes the project recognisable.

The letters of the logo have a degradation of colour, which refers to the evolution of the project.

Figure 2-1 - Logo - main version

The logo can be presented in different formats and colour variation, depending on the specific needs of the communication material. For instance, social networks such as LinkedIn or Twitter require two profile pictures, a small one and a long horizontal one. Regarding ePLANET, the small one is usually simpler. It has no letters and is represented by the colourful dots in yellow, blue and red which normally surround the first letter of ePLANET. The logo used in the horizontal image is the usual one.

Figure 2-2 - Logo - monocolour versions

Figure 2-3 - Logo, negative effect version

Figure 2-4 - Logo, short version

3 Primary colour palette

The ePLANET logo uses a set of colours that can be combined in different ways.

	CMYK 100 15 30 25 RGB 0 116 138 HEX #00748A				
	CMYK 90 69 0 0 RGB 24 86 160 HEX #1856A0				
	CMYK 100 100 25 25 RGB 19 35 91 HEX #13235B				
	CMYK 100 20 0 0 RGB 0 158 224 HEX #009EE0				
	CMYK 53 42 39 4 RGB 134 136 137 HEX #868889				

CMYK 90|69|0|0
RGB 24|86|160
HEX #1856A0

CMYK 73|0|58|0
RGB 69|178|138
HEX #45B28A

Figure 3-1 - ePLANET palette of colours

4 Typography in use

The typography used for the documents of ePLANET project will be Trebuchet MS, even though Calibri or Arial can be used alternatively.

abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxy
z
ABCDEFGHIJKLMN
OPQRSTUVWXYZ
0123456789,;. :{[] }?!

Figure 4-1 - Trebuchet MS font

5 Slides template

Different slides have been defined, to maximise the compatibility of the logo and the palette of colours with the overall readability of the content.

Figure 5-1 - Templates for initial, text, and final slides

6 Deliverable template

Project deliverables need to respect some specific requirements from the European Commission. A specific template for ePLANET deliverables has been created in MsWORD, aiming to define a common graphical layout framework respecting these EC requirements and increasing the coherence within all the deliverables that will be prepared during project duration.

Figure 6-1 - Template for ePLANET deliverables

